

COMPOSITE CASTINGS REINFORCED BY TiC PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

The authors present three different methods of in situ fabrication composite casting. The synthesis of a reinforcing phase in all methods was initiated by the high temperature of the liquid metal. Two of the presented methods of obtaining composite reinforcement in Fe alloys could be good candidates for obtaining materials used in an industrial application working under ultra-high wear abrasive conditions. Additionally, the authors present a new method of stabilizing local composite reinforcement in a ferrous alloy. A third of methods present a casting process that allows them to obtain an aluminum base composite reinforced by nanoparticles of TiC. Investigations of the fabricated materials were carried out with the application of phase analysis, light microscopy (LM), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

1 INTRODUCTION

From the point of view of designing products, all engineering materials have equal rights. Multi-criteria optimization constitutes the basis of selecting materials with the best technological and functional properties, the lowest production and processing costs, and the maintenance of the product. Composite materials are widely used in many industrial fields. This group of materials can be classified according to the matrix type. One of the most popular and important types of composite materials are metal matrix composites (MMC). Due to their total freedom of design, MMCs can be applied in many industrial applications. Metals or alloys such as aluminum, magnesium, titanium, cast steel, cast iron, etc. can be used as a matrix of the mentioned materials depending on the operating conditions [1].

The manufacture of metal matrix composites reinforced by TiC particles has been extensively discussed in many scientific studies. As a strengthening phase, titanium carbide is characterized by high hardness (from 3000 to 3200 HV), a high melting point (3067°C), thermodynamic and chemical stability, wear resistance, modulus of elasticity (460 GPa), shear modulus (40 GPa), and good corrosion resistance. A number of the above-mentioned properties have contributed to the fact that TiC is often selected as a phase reinforcement of a many kinds of MMCs [2,3].

Abrasive wear is one of the main factors, resulting in the elimination of thousands of tons of the cast elements of machines and devices annually [4]. A selected group of commercial alloys such as manganese, martensitic steel, or white chromium cast iron constitute the most popular materials that are used in the production of elements that are resistant to abrasive wear [5,6]. Due to the still-growing working parameters, economic aspects, and fast development of new types of materials, their properties are insufficient. Metal matrix composites based on Fe alloys reinforced by ceramic particles

are good candidates for replacing commercial materials in order to increase the lifetime of cast structural elements. They are characterized by a good combination of a matrix with good plasticity and the high hardness of the ceramic phase in the form of TiC carbides [7].

An interesting group of composites seems to be metal matrix composites based on an aluminum matrix. Aluminum alloys reinforced with various ceramic particles are universally called aluminum matrix composites (AMCs). AMCs exhibit excellent properties such as low density, high stiffness, high conductivity, high toughness, and a high strength-to-weight ratio. The application of TiC as a phase reinforcement can enhance the hardness and lightness of AMCs, which makes it potential for a variety of weight-critical engineering applications [8]. The properties of aluminum matrix composites mentioned above and a wide spectrum of their potential applications in the aerospace, automobile, transport, and military industries contribute to the fact that they have become the subject of a great many papers [9,10,11]. The majority of these studies have concentrated on aluminum composite properties reinforced with micro-sized particles. A new trend in the studies indicates the significant advantage of nanoparticles as compared to micro-sized as a prospective alternative of the phase reinforcement of aluminum composites [12].

For producing such materials, these methods allow us to obtain a metal matrix composite of such techniques as laser plating, thermal spraying, hardfacing, welding (TIG - tungsten inert gas), powder metallurgy, mechanical alloying, stir casting, squeeze casting, spray deposition, etc. [13,14]. The methods for obtaining the composite materials mentioned above have several drawbacks, such as obtaining heterogeneous structures, low process accuracy, the possible occurrence of porosities and inclusions, and significant limits in designing elements with complex geometries [15]. Applied only rarely, an interesting solution is the application of casting technologies. One of the processes that allows us to obtain composite castings is self-propagating high-temperature synthesis in a bath [16,17], which is the modification of the standard self-propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS) reaction applied in powder metallurgy [18]. In this method, the synthesis reaction of the selected ceramic phase is initiated by the heat supplied by the liquid alloy at a temperature above 1200°C. A major challenge in the material's science is the design of composite materials on a cast aluminum-based matrix reinforced with the in situ manufacture of TiC nanoparticles during the casting process. TiC nanoparticles can influence the blocking of the grain growth during the solidification process of a casting, which influences the decrease of the grain size and increases the tensile strength (Re). The presence of nanosized TiC particles increase the yield strength and Young module (E) cast components. The mentioned dependence was a main reason for attempting to fabricate composite materials based on pure aluminum.

The authors of this paper present three methods of manufacturing composite castings reinforced by TiC particles based on Fe-alloys and an aluminum matrix.

2 METHODS OF OBTAINING IN SITU COMPOSITE TI/FE-ALLOYS

Depending on operating conditions of the given structural detail and its wearing intensity, there are three possibilities of forming three composite forms in castings.

Over the past few years, many researchers have presented the results of manufacturing composite reinforcement-type TiC/Fe-alloys. Most of the methods were based on preparing green compacts that contain the substrates of TiC and places in the mold cavity in the further part of the described process. The obtained materials were characterized from the point of view of structure, microstructure, mechanical properties, etc.; however, none of them presented the macrostructure of the composite castings [19-21]. These results are the effect of the course of the synthesis reaction of TiC, which is a highly exothermic formation (with an enthalpy of -187 kJ/mol) [22]. Intensive energy production in the form of the generated heat results in the local increase of the temperature of the liquid metal, significantly intensifying the phenomenon of infiltration within the local composite reinforcements. Thus, the TiC is separated by a liquid casting alloy due to their lower density (they move within the casting). This phenomenon is called composite zone fragmentation. In this paper, the authors describe a new method for obtaining stable and homogeneous composite reinforcements with a moderator application. The moderator should be defined as a mixture of metal and non-metal powder, which decreases the amount of produced energy during the TiC synthesis process [23, 24].

2.1 Composite layer

The technological process of manufacturing a composite layer based on covering a mold cavity with reactive castings coatings [25].

2.2 Fabrication of composite layer

The casting coatings for the in situ fabrication of the TiC/Fe-type composite layers were prepared on the basis of CMC aqueous solutions with 2% concentrations along with the addition of substrates from the TiC-forming reaction. These substrates were in powder form; i.e., graphite (Cgr) and titanium (Ti). The weight ratio of the aqueous CMC solution to the TiC-formation substrates was 1:2. The mixture necessary for producing the in situ TiC was prepared at an atomic ratio of 50% Ti : 50% C. Titanium powder from the Stanchem Company of Poland (purity – 99.95%; average diameter – 44 m) and flake graphite from the Sinograf Company of Poland (purity – above 96%; average diameter – 3 m) were used. CMC was introduced as a binding material and stabilizer to improve the rheological properties and wettability between the composite coating and sand mold cavity.

The first stage involved covering the casting mold cavity with the selected coatings. Then, the dried mold was poured with liquid cast steel of the following chemical composition: 0.2%C; 0.35% Si; 0.72% Mn; 0.1% Cr; Fe residue at a temperature of 1823 K. The technological process of fabricating composite layer-type TiC/Fe alloys is presented in Figure 1.

The samples were taken from the ready castings. The microstructural investigations were performed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on an FEI Versa 3D microscope using the detector of backscattered electrons (BSE).

Figure 1: Steps of technological process of fabrication composite layer in steel casting

2.3 Microstructure of composite layer reinforced with TiC particles

The microstructure investigations were started by putting pictures of the microstructure together, which illustrated the cross-section of the produced composite layer of the TiC/Fe type (Fig. 2). The observations indicate that the layer structures are not homogenous at their whole lengths. As a result, internal zones are obtained without reinforcing phases. This is a result of the fragmentation phenomena described in Paragraph 2. The produced layer is locally of a maximum thickness of 1.5 mm. The presence of the porosity in the microstructure is connected with the application of CMC as a binder of the composite coatings. During direct contact with the liquid metal, this organic material was degraded; as a result, gases were emitted.

Each of the individual powder compositions (A to I – indicated in Table 1) were mixed for six hours. Next, the mixtures were cold pressed using a uniaxial press at a pressure of 550 MPa. The obtained compacts, whose dimensions were 10 x 50 x Y mm (where Y = the dimension as a result of the compatibility of the individual mixtures), were placed in a mold cavity according to the scheme presented in Figure 3. The sand mold was poured with liquid cast steel. The pouring temperature of the liquid alloy was 1823 K.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of mold along with compacts for LCR manufacturing

The readied cast product was cut into pieces in order to take a sample that contained a composite zone and base alloy. The sample was subjected to grinding and polishing before it was investigated in the metallographic, structural, and mechanical test examinations. The metallographic examinations were carried out with the application of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using an FEI Versa 3D microscope and BSE detector.

3.2 Macrostructure and microstructure of local composite reinforcement

The macrostructure of the casting with local composite reinforcement fabricated in situ is presented in Figure 4. Small casting defects are visible on the surface of the casting. The conducted observation indicated that the addition of moderator stabilized the synthesis reaction of the TiC. Up to 50 wt.% of the moderator in the local composite reinforcement was not obtained in the casting. Increasing the amount of the moderator stabilizes the dimension of the local composite reinforcement and has a marked influence on their homogeneity. These results confirm the obtained results of the researchers in their publications and prove that the presented solution is correct. A good method for determining the influence of the addition of the moderator on stabilizing the composite zone is observing the transition area between the local composite reinforcement and the casting core (base alloy). The transition area of LCR A and B are not continuous. The fragmentation process of the LCR has a marked influence on the final properties of the composite zone. After adding between 70 and 97 wt.% of the moderator, the transition area seems to be sharper and takes the form of a straight line. The introduction of the moderator seems to be quite important in forming the microstructure of the composite reinforcement.

Figure 4: Macrostructure of casting with local composite reinforcement manufactured in cast steel casting

4 CAST IN SITU NANOCOMPOSITES TiC/AL TYPE

The last method allows us to produce the so-called cast composite 3D type. The reinforcing phase produced in situ is equally distributed in the whole casting volume.

4.1 Experiment

The mixture of substrates necessary for TiC in situ formation was prepared with an atomic ratio of 1:1. The commercial titanium powder by Stanchem, Poland (99.95% purity, 44 μm average diameter) and flake graphite by Sinograf, Poland (purity above 96%, 3 μm average diameter) were used. The moderator of the TiC synthesis reaction in the form of aluminum powder by Benda-Lutz (99.7% purity, 32 μm) was introduced into the mixture of titanium and carbon powders. The chemical composition of the compacts used for the synthesis reaction of the aluminum composite is shown in Table 2. The prepared weighted portion was subjected to mixing with no air access for two hours in a mixer in order to homogenize their properties. Afterwards, they were dried at a temperature of 423 K for two hours in a furnace. The last stage consisted of cold pressing the prepared powder mixtures under 500 MPa pressure using a uniaxial hydraulic press. The manufactured compacts were cut into small pieces. In the next step, the readied parts of the compacts were placed into metal bath. The casting process was conducted in a Balzer's vacuum furnace in an argon atmosphere. The aluminum was a matrix of manufacturing composites.

No.	Internal symbol of compacts	Weight TiC reactants, wt. %
1	404/7/IC6	2
2	437/5X/IC6	5
3	482/IC6	10
4	437/3	0

Table 2: Base information about casting process.

The final casting was cut in order to take samples. Before the metallographic and structural examinations, the samples were subjected to grinding and polishing. The microstructural characterization of the materials was performed by a Leica DM IRM light microscope (LM) and FEI ESEM XL 30 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an EDAX GEMINI 400 X-ray energy dispersive spectrometer. Imaging with backscattered electron mode (BSE mode) gave detailed information about the microstructure and phase contrast, while dispersive X-ray spectroscopy analyses (EDS) were used to examine the chemical composition of the phases. The SEM observations were performed using an accelerating voltage of 12 kV. The samples for the SEM observations were prepared by mechanical polishing and were additionally etched using a Keller electrolyte to expose the grain boundaries for optical microscope observations. The identification of the phases was performed by high-energy synchrotron radiation ($\lambda=0.014235$ nm) using beam line P07 at DESY in Hamburg, Germany.

4.2 Results and discussion

4.2.1 X-ray analysis

The results of the XRD phase analysis of the fabricated in situ composite reinforced with nanoparticles of TiC and aluminum are presented in Figure 5. In the tested materials, two main phases were identified: aluminum (which was the matrix of the composite materials), and nanoparticles of TiC. Furthermore, TiAl_3 was created during synthesis in the liquid alloy phase. This intermetallic phase is a “by-product” of the synthesis reaction of the TiC. Additionally, the presence of an

Fe₂Al₃Si₃ phase was observed in the taken sample. The mentioned phase rises from the chemical elements of the Series 1000 alloy. The intensity of the peaks originated from the crystallographic plane of the TiC increase according to the weight content of the pure substrates of TiC (2, 5, and 10 wt.%).

Figure 5: High-energy X-ray diffraction patterns for aluminium matrix alloy and composite materials.

4.2.2 Microstructure

Figure 6 shows a set of optical micrographs for (a) the aluminum 1000 matrix alloy and composites containing (b) 2, (c) 5, and (d) 10 wt.% of the substrates (Ti+C). The microstructure of the aluminum matrix alloy is typical for casting alloys and consists of (i) smaller equiaxed grains formed adjacent to the cold mold, (ii) columnar grains with the growth direction perpendicular to the mold, and (iii) larger equiaxed grains in the center of the casting. The grain size was found to be from hundreds of micrometers to a few millimeters, whereas the composites show finer microstructures, with average grain sizes of 170 ± 57 , 150 ± 42 , and 140 ± 40 μm for the composites with 2, 5, and 10 wt.% of substrates, respectively. The size of the grains decreases with increases of the substrates, which is connected to the formation of TiC particles suppressing the grain growth of the aluminum matrix. Interestingly, the composite castings do not show a columnar grain zone (as opposed to the aluminum matrix alloy).

Figure 6: (a) Set of LM for aluminum matrix alloy and composites containing (b) 2, (c) 5, and (d) 10 wt.% of Ti+C substrates

Figure 7 demonstrates scanning electron microscopy backscattered electron (SEM/BSE) images comparing the aluminum matrix alloys with the composites at two different magnifications. TiC particles were found for all of the composite materials. It is obvious that their concentration increases with additional amounts of substrates; however, the TiC particles were preferentially located at the grain boundaries for the composites with lower concentrations of substrates (2 and 5 wt.%), while the sample with 10 wt.% of substrates shows a uniform homogenous distribution of the reinforcement. However, based on the SEM/EDS method, additional unwanted phases other than TiC particles were identified. The first one was an intermetallic TiAl_3 phase in the form of longish plates (sometimes arranged in “crosses”) appearing inside the aluminum matrix grains. The existence of intermetallic phases is usually undesirable because they are brittle and can impoverish the mechanical properties. The second phase was an $\text{Fe}_2\text{Al}_3\text{Si}_3$ phase, which is very typical for aluminum-based materials. Iron is well-known as the most common observed impurity of aluminum alloys.

Figure 7: (a),(b) SEM/BSE images at different magnifications for aluminum matrix alloy as well as composites containing (c),(d) 2, (e),(f) 5, and (g),(h) 10 wt.% of Ti+C substrates

5 CONCLUSIONS

The methods of preparing composite castings discussed in this article allow us to obtain functional materials with reinforced ceramics based on Fe-C (cast iron, cast steel) or aluminum. The fragmentation of the composite layer and local composite reinforcement was identified. The authors presented a method of limiting this unfavorable phenomenon. An interesting part of the paper constituted the presentation of the method of obtaining a cast composite reinforced with TiC nanoparticles. In each material, phase ceramics with nano-sized ceramic particles were identified. The surface fraction of the phase ceramic depended on the weight content of the TiC substrates. The sizes of the grains decrease with increased amounts of substrates, which is connected to the formation of TiC particles suppressing the grain growth of the aluminum matrix. Interestingly, composite castings do not show columnar grains zone (as opposed to the aluminum matrix alloy).

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REFERENCES

- [1] M.P. Behera, T. Dougherty, S. Singammani, Conventional and Additive Manufacturing with Metal Matrix Composites: A Perspective, *Procedia Manufacturing*, 30, 2019, pp. 159-166
- [2] J. Lee, D. Lee, M.H. Song, W. Rhee, H.K. Ryu, S.H. Hong, In situ synthesis of TiC/Fe alloy composites with high strength and hardness by reactive sintering, *Journal of Materials Science and Technology*, 34/8, 2018, pp. 1397-1404
- [3] Y. Liang, Z. Han, Z. Zhang, X. Li, L. Ren, Effect of Cu content in Cu-TiB₄C system on fabricating TiC/TiB₂ particulates locally reinforced steel matrix composites, *Materials and Design*, 40, 2012, pp. 64-69
- [4] J. Rendon, M. Olsson, Abrasive wear resistance of some commercial abrasion resistant steels evaluated by laboratory test methods, *Wear*, 267, 2009, pp. 2055-2061
- [5] S.W. Hu, Y.G. Zhao, Z. Wang, Y.G. Li, Q.C. Jiang, Fabrication of in situ TiC locally reinforced manganese steel matrix composite via combustion synthesis during casting, *Materials and design*, 44, 2013, pp. 340-345
- [6] E. Olejnik, Ł. Szymański, P. Kurtyka, T. Tokarski, B. Grabowska, P. Czapla, Hardness and wear resistance of TiC-Fe-Cr locally reinforcement produced in cast steel, *Archives of Foundry Engineering*, 16, 2016, 89-94
- [7] S. Zhou, X. Zeng, Growth characteristic and mechanism of carbides precipitated in WC-Fe composite coatings by laser induction hybrid rapid cladding, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 505 (2), 2010, pp. 685-691
- [8] M. Penchal Reddy, M.A. Himyan, F. Ubaid, R.A. Shakoor, M. Vyasraj, P. Gururaj, M. Yusuf, A.M.A. Mohamed, M. Gupta, Enhancing thermal and mechanical response of aluminium using nanolength scale TiC ceramic reinforcement, *Ceramics International*, 44, 2018, 9247-9254
- [9] W. Liu, C. Cao, J. Xu, X. Wang, X. Li, Molten salt assisted solidification nanoprocessing of Al-TiC nanocomposites, *Materials Letters*, 185, 2016, pp. 392-395
- [10] J. Jebeen Moses, I. Dinaharan, S. Joseph Sekhar, Production of influence of process parameters on tensile strength of AA6061/TiC aluminium matrix composite produced using stir casting, *Transaction of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*, 26, 2016, pp. 1498-1511
- [11] I. Manivannan, S. Ranganathan, S. Gopalakannan, S. Suresh, K. Nagakarthigan, R. Jubendradass, Tribological and surface behavior of silicon carbide reinforced aluminium matrix nanocomposite, *Surface and Interfaces*, 8, 2017, 127-136

- [12] K. Jeshurun Lijay, J. David Raja Selvam, I. Dinaharan, S.J. Vijay, Microstructure and mechanical properties characterization of AA6061/TiC aluminium matrix composites synthesized by in situ reaction of silicon carbide and potassium fluotitanate, *Transactions of Nonferrous Society of China*, 26, 2016, pp. 1791-1800
- [13] M. Cabeza, I. Feijoo, P. Merino, G. Pena, M.C. Pereze, S. Cruz, P. Rey, Effect of high energy ball milling on the morphology, microstructure and properties of nan-sized TiC particles-reinforced 6005A aluminium alloy matrix composite, *Powder Technology*, 321, 2017, pp. 31-43
- [14] L.M. Berger, Application of hard metals as thermal spray coating, *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, 49, 2015, pp. 350-364
- [15] L. Zhong, T. Wu, X. Zhang, S. Fan, L. Wang, S. Chen, In situ preparation of titanium carbide layer on grey cast iron, *Materials Science*, 21/4, 2015, pp. 586-589
- [16] E. Fraś, A. Janas, A. Kolbus, E. Olejnik, Cast in situ composite of Ni₃Al/MeC type, 19/2, 2009, pp. 586-589
- [17] E. Fraś, A. Janas, A. Kolbus, E. Olejnik, Odlewane kompozyty “in situ” Ni₃Al/MeC (Me-W,Zr), *Archiwum Odlewnictwa*, 6/8, 2006, pp. 317-324
- [18] Y.F. Yang, H.Y. Wang, Y.H. Liang, R.Y. Zhao, Q.C. Jiang, Effect of C particle size on the porous formation of TiC particulate locally reinforced steel matrix composite via the SHS reaction of Ni-Ti-Csystem during casting, *Materials Science and Engineering A*, 474, 2008, 355- 362
- [19] Y. Wang, X. Zhang, G. Zeng, F. Li, In situ production of Fe-VC and Fe-TiC surface composites by cast-sinteting. *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, 32, 2001, pp. 281-286
- [20] X. Zhang, W. Lu, D. Zhang, R. Wu, In situ technique for synthesizing (TiB + TiC)/Ti composites. *Scripta Materialia*, 41/1, 1999, pp. 39-46
- [21] Q.F. Guang, Q.C. Jiang, Y.Q. Zhao, C.H. Liu, In situ production of Fe-TiC composites by self-propagative high temperature synthesis reaction in liquid iron alloy, *ISIJ International*, 42/6, 2002, pp. 673-675
- [22] A.G. Merzhanov, Combustion process that synthesize materials, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 56, 1996, pp. 222-241
- [23] E. Olejnik, Ł. Szymański, T. Tokarski, B. Opitek, P. Kurtyka, Local composite reinforcements of TiC/FeMn type obtained in situ in steel castings, *Archives of Civil and Mechanical Engineering*, 19, 2019, pp. 997-1005
- [24] E. Olejnik, T. Tokarski, G. Sikora, S. Sobula, W. Maziarz, Ł. Szymański, B. Grabowska, The effect of Fe addition on fragmentation phenomena, macrostructure, microstructure, and hardness of TiC-Fe local reinforcements fabricated in situ in steel casting, *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, 50/2, 2019, pp. 975-986
- [25] Ł. Szymański, E. Olejnik, T. Tokarski, P. Kurtyka, D. Drożyński, S. Żymankowska – Kumon, Reactive casting coatings for obtaining in situ composite layers based on Fe alloy, *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 350, 2018, pp. 346-358